

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

STUDY TO KNOW THE COMMON BILE DUCT STONES ON ENDOSCOPIC RETROGRADE CHOLANGIO PANCREATOGRAPHY IN GALLSTONE PANCREATITIS WITH DERANGED LIVER FUNCTION

¹Dr Noor Fatima Malik, ²Dr Ayesha Arif, ³Dr Muhammad Ahmed Arif
^{1,2,3} Lahore Medical and Dental College, Lahore

Article Received: October 2020

Accepted: November 2020

Published: December 2020

Abstract:

Objective: To determine the frequency of CBD stone on ERCP in gall stone pancreatitis with deranged liver function. If decrease frequency of CBD stone found then recommendations can be made to reduce the unnecessary ERCP and it's procedure related complications like perforation and hemorrhage.

Study Design: Single center, non-probability consecutive, cross sectional study

Place and Duration of Study: This study was conducted at the Department of Gastroenterology, Jinnah Hospital Lahore for the duration of six months from February 2020 to August 2020.

Materials and Methods: Total 227 patients with deranged liver function test, serum amylase level of greater than 300 U/l, upper abdominal pain and gallstones on the trans-abdominal ultrasonography, were included. All patients were undergone ERCP. Descriptive statistics of the data was computed.

Results: There were 149 male and 78 female patients. Overall, raised total bilirubin was 62.6%, raised alkaline phosphate was 33.5%, and raised gamma GT was 40.5% patients. CBD stone in ERCP was found in 26.0% patients. Significant association of raised total bilirubin, raised alkaline phosphate, raised gamma GT, and serum amylase with CBD stone in ERCP was observed.

Conclusion: Patients with gallstone pancreatitis and deranged liver function test had increased risk of CBD stones. ERCP is the gold-standard for evaluation of morphological changes in the pancreas.

Key Words: Common Bile Duct Stones, ERCP, Gallstone Pancreatitis, Deranged Liver Function

Corresponding author:

Dr Noor Fatima Malik,

Lahore Medical and Dental College, Lahore

QR code

Please cite this article in press Noor Fatima Malik et al, *Study To Know The Common Bile Duct Stones On Endoscopic Retrograde Cholangio Pancreatography In Gallstone Pancreatitis With Deranged Liver Function.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(12).

INTRODUCTION:

In adult population, the percentage of occurrence of gallstones ranges from 6%-10%¹. It has been indicated that 3%-14.7% of patients with gallstones are found to be with concurrent common bile duct (CBD) stones². For the management of gallstones "Gold Standard" is laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) but no agreement for treatment is there of CBD stones. In the age of open surgery, here the treatment is straight-forward; there is greater probability for the high mortality and morbidity if open cholecystectomy is to be conducted with open CBD exploration. With the arrival of minimal invasive and noninvasive techniques, choice of pre-operative ERCP tailed by LC arose as acceptable treatment. Main drawbacks of ERCP are that it is the procedure which is performed in two stages and is there are life threatening complications in it i.e. bleeding, pancreatitis and duodenal perforation^{2,3}.

It has been reported that more than 230,000 patients were provided the treatment for acute pancreatitis at hospitals of the United States in 2005⁴. Recent literature indicates an growth in the occurrence of acute pancreatitis, and at some places, higher rate of occurrence have been projected substantially in the comparison of occurrence that are previously reported, whereas, case-fatalities have remained unchanging since the period of 1970⁵. Growth in the occurrence of acute pancreatitis may be caused because of increasing occurrence of obesity, a risk factor for the growth of gallstones and gallstone pancreatitis⁶.

Heavy financial load on the health care system and noteworthy physiologic stress on the patient is conferred by the acute pancreatitis. It is indicated by the research that the average cost of the hospitalization for acute pancreatitis was estimated to be \$9870⁷. It has been also indicated that acute pancreatitis has been made responsible in United States for \$ 2.2 billion as the expenditure on healthcare per year. The mean duration of patients to stay at the hospital having acute pancreatitis is around 5 to 6 days^{5,8}.

The part of liver in the body is to perform the various function i.e. biochemical, excretory and synthetic functions etc. global functions of liver can be detected by the single biochemical test. Series of tests are often employed by all of the laboratories in order to detect and manage the diseases of liver these tests are known as the "Liver function tests"⁹.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This single center, non-probability consecutive, cross sectional study was conducted at the Department of Gastroenterology, Jinnah Hospital Lahore for the duration of six months from February 2020 to August 2020. Study population in the inclusion criteria was either gender with age of 18 to 65 years, who were presented with gallstone pancreatitis with deranged liver function test of duration 1 to 7 days. Acute gallstone pancreatitis` diagnosis was grounded on the existence of pain in upper abdomen, a serum amylase level of >300 U/l (25-100 U/l), and gallstones on the trans abdominal ultrasonography, deranged LFTs (as mentioned in operational definitions) on admission were included in the study. Patient was undergone ERCP & was used as a therapeutic and diagnostic tool as well. Informed written consent was taken before enrolment. Exclusion criteria were followed strictly to avoid confounding variables.

Statistical analysis: Data analysis was carried out in the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 17. Frequencies and percentages were computed for categorical variables like gender; CBD stones, raised total bilirubin, raised alkaline phosphate and raised Gamma GT. Values were presented as mean standard deviation for continuous variables like age, duration of gallstone pancreatitis, and serum amylase. Effect modifier like age, gender, serum amylase, raised total bilirubin, raised alkaline phosphate raised Gamma GT and duration of Gall stone pancreatitis were controlled through stratification. For post stratification Chi-Square test was applied. Confidence interval was kept to be 95% and the level of significance was kept to be 5%.

RESULTS:

Total 227 patients of either gender, age 18 to 65 years with gallstone pancreatitis and deranged liver function test of duration 1 to 7 days were included in the study to determine the frequency of CBD stones detected on ERCP. Descriptive statistics were calculated. Stratification was done to see the effect of modifiers on outcome. Post stratification chi square test was applied considering $p \leq 0.05$ as significant.

There were 149 male and 78 female patients. The frequency distribution is presented in Table-2. The mean age of study subjects was 40.96 ± 11.92 years, mean serum amylase was 1012.97 ± 251.81 U/l & the mean duration of gall stone pancreatitis was 2.58 ± 0.85 days. The distribution of age is presented in Graph-1. The descriptive statistics of age, serum amylase & duration of gall stone pancreatitis is presented in Table-1. The results showed that in all

227 patients, raised total bilirubin was found in 62.6% patients, raised alkaline phosphate was found in 33.5% patients, and raised gamma GT detected about 40.5% among the patients, as shown in table-2. The final outcome i.e. CBD stone in ERCP was found about 26.0% among the patients, as shown in Table-2. The descriptive statistics of age, serum amylase, and duration of gall stone pancreatitis according to the CBD in ERCP were calculated. The

results of descriptive statistics are presented in Table-3.

The results showed that significant association of serum amylase ($P=0.002$) with CBD stone in ERCP was observed. No significant association of age, gender and duration of gall stone pancreatitis was observed with CBD stone in ERCP. In table-3 and table-4 the detail of results is present.

Table No.1: Descriptive statistics of age, serum amylase, duration (days) of gall stone pancreatitis (n=227)

	Age (years)	Serum amylase (U/l)	Duration of gallstone pancreatitis(days)
Mean $\pm$ SD	40.96 $\pm$ 11.92	1012.97 $\pm$ 251.81	2.58 $\pm$ 0.85
95%CI (LB – UB)	39.41 – 42.52	980.04 – 1045.91	2.47 – 2.69
Median (IQR)	40.00 (17)	1047.00 (189)	3.00 (1)
Range	44	1762	5
Minimum	19	473	1
Maximum	63	2235	6

Table No.2: Frequency distribution of gender, overall raised total bilirubin, overall raised alkaline phosphate, overall raised gamma GT, CBD stones on ERCP (n=227)

Gender	Frequency (n=227)	Percentage (%)	
Male	149	65.6%	
Female	78	34.4%	
Total	227	100%	
Variable	Yes	No	Total
Over all raised total bilirubin	142(62.6%)	85(37.4%)	227(100%)
Over all raised alkaline phosphate	76(33.5%)	151(66.5%)	227(100%)
Over all raised gamma GT	92(40.5%)	135(59.5%)	227(100%)
CBD stones on ERCP	59(26%)	168(74%)	227(100%)

Table No.3: Descriptive statistics of age, serum amylase, duration of gall stone pancreatitis according to CBD stone in ERCP (n=227)

	Age		Serum amylase		Duration of gallstone pancreatitis	
	YES (n=59)	NO (n=168)	YES (n=59)	NO (n=168)	YES (n=59)	NO (n=168)
Mean $\pm$ SD	43.83 $\pm$ 13.09	39.96 $\pm$ 11.35	1123.95 $\pm$ 295.67	974.00 $\pm$ 222.64	2.60 $\pm$ 0.85	2.60 $\pm$ 0.85
95% CI (LB – UB)	40.42 – 47.24	38.23 – 41.69	1046.90 – 1201.00	940.00 – 1007.91	2.47 – 2.73	2.47 – 2.73
Median (IQR)	46.00 (19)	39.00 (17)	1080.00 (112)	1036.00 (200)	3.00 (1)	3.00 (1)
Range	44	44	1597	1627	5	5
Minimum	19	19	638	473	1	1
Maximum	63	63	2235	2100	6	6

Table No.4: Frequency and association of CBD stone in ERCP according to gender (n=227)

	CBD IN ERCP			P-value
	YES (n=59)	NO (n=168)	TOTAL	
Male (n=149)	35	114	149	0.235**
Female (n=78)	24	54	78	
TOTAL	59	168	227	

DISCUSSION:

It's known from centuries that the pancreatitis can be caused by gallstones by the blockage of ampulla of vater. The biliary pancreatitis resulted because of gallstones temporary obstruction, then they passed freely into the duodenum. The more problematic suffering for patients will be there because of gallstone pancreatitis, whom having persistent ampullary or bile duct stone. The harshness of biliary pancreatitis and risk of cholangitis could be decreased by removal of persistent stones.¹⁰the study from Saudi Arabia has underlined gallstone as 68.5% for causing acute pancreatitis.¹¹ whereas the occurrence of pancreatitis in USA is reported about 40% in all cases.¹²

The removal of any CBD stone is considered as practicing treatment for gallstone pancreatitis which is followed by cholecystectomy which resist further occurrence of acute gallstone pancreatitis. If surgery delayed in case of patients recovering from the initial attack of gallstones pancreatitis would have higher risk for next attack up to 30-fold in general population.¹³ while having index admission in hospital the performance of cholecystectomy should be considered standard of care.¹⁴the biliary duck assessment and clearance should be remained as a subject of conversation between clinicians before assessing cholecystectomy. The tools for bile duct should be adapted or optional for its evaluation and clearance before cholecystectomy are serial LET, MRCP, EUS, repetitive or selected preoperative ERCP and intraoperative cholangiogram (IOC).¹²¹⁵the bile duct stone is most commonly found among the most of patient which is included normally in the history of gallstone pancreatitis.¹⁶

In Al-Qahtani et al study¹⁷ the selection of patients done for preoperative ERCP assisted by using tool like LFT. A study has shown which was conducted by a team of surgeons that the early unbalanced LETS results in an acceptable indication for the

ERCP intervention prior to laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

LFT was used as the tool for assessment for the selection of patients for preoperative ERCP, in the research conducted by Al-Qahtani et al¹⁷. Initial unbalanced LFTs were considered by some surgical teams as an acceptable marker for ERCP interference former to laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Patients of group A were submitted to ERCP grounded on the day of their admission unbalanced LFTs. In only eight patients, endoscopic retrograde cholangiogram was therapeutic (stone n=5, sludge n=3); whereas, six patients (5%) had complications associated with ERCP. Where ERCP was late until repeat LFTs in the patients of group B, outcomes were available, only eight patients (5%) who continued to have unbalanced LFTs were referred to ERCP and in all patients it was therapeutic (stone n=5, sludge n=3). There were no problems associated with ERCP in the patients. Whereas, 3 patients on whom preoperative ERCP was not conducted, were presented later with complications associated with recurring stone within the period of two years. Therefore, this research has indicated that by the use of LFT as an average in the selection of preoperative ERCP was significantly decreased the complications and number of unnecessary ERCP. Furthermore, it indicates that by omission of ERCP in those patients whose LFT quickly enhanced towards normal, the long term complication risk due to missed stone is slight. In our surgical department, the marker for preoperative ERCP grounded on initial unbalanced LFTs is no longer exercised¹⁷.

It has been demonstrated by intraoperative cholangiogram that the unsuspected CBD stones` occurrence ranges from 2.8-5.8% in those patients having imaging and normal preoperative LFT¹⁸. It has been concluded by Shayan et al. that occurrence of stones of bile duct in those patients who are improving from mild to

moderate acute gallstone pancreatitis with imaging and normal preoperative LFT is not found to be significantly higher (7.6%) in the comparison of those patients experiencing laparoscopic cholecystectomy for symptomatic cholelithiasis¹². Quite similar rate of stone of bile duct, in the patients who are experiencing cholecystectomy for symptomatic cholelithiasis or gallstone pancreatitis has been described as well¹⁹. In a research, the missed stone occurrence in patients having normalized preoperative LFTs was found to be low (2%). In the research conducted by Ito et al.²⁰, the occurrence of recurring acute pancreatitis because of retained CBD stones in those patients who did not experience preoperative ERCP or IOC during surgery was found to be 8%. In the investigation which was conducted by Al-Qahtani et al only 3 patients (2%) without preoperative ERCP developed events of bilio-pancreas because of missed CBD stones.

The rate of complication of ERCP with ES as reported in another study was 4.95% with the rate of mortality is equal to 0.12%²¹. Whereas, no mortality was found in this study. Therefore, a repetitive preoperative ERCP in patients could be safely skipped who were improving from biliary pancreatitis if their initial unbalanced liver functions returned near to normal or normal in the period of three to four days from the beginning of disease. The tenacity of CBD stones in acute gallstone pancreatitis did not contribute to continuing or pancreatic inflammation worsening^{21,22}. A research conducted by Al-Qahtani et al,¹⁷ in which all patients with continuous greater LFT after the duration of 72 hours that experienced ERCP were indicated to suffer from either stones or sludge. Local of systemic complications were developed by none of them.

In case of ECRP indications of these patients the use of advanced tools could be helpful. The rate in conversation of open surgery would be increased by routine IOC because of limited experience in survey of laparoscopic CBD. Moreover, the unimportant CBD exploration could be leaded by wrong positive IOC. The re-evaluation of bilio-pancreatic symptoms which developed in patients afterward will be done by MRCP or ERCP even after a normal IOC. The improvement from moderate gallstone pancreatitis in case of patients done easily in cholecystectomy without IOC.

CONCLUSION:

Patients with gallstone pancreatitis and deranged liver function test had increased risk of CBD stones. ERCP is the gold-standard for evaluation of morphological changes in the pancreas.

REFERENCES:

1. Sharma A, Dahiya P, Khullar R, Soni V, Baijal M, Chowbey PK. Management of common bile duct stones in the laparoscopic era. *Indian J Surg* 2012; 74:264-269.
2. Shojaiefard A, Esmaeilzadeh M, Ghafouri A, Mehri A. Various techniques for the surgical treatment of common bile duct stones: a meta review. *Gastroenterol Res Pract* 2009;2009: 840208.
3. Lee HM, Min SK, Lee HK. Long-term results of laparoscopic common bile duct exploration by choledochotomy for choledocholithiasis: 15-year experience from a single center. *Ann Surg Treat Res* 2014; 86:1-6.
4. DeFrances CJ, Cullen KA, Kozak LJ. National Hospital Discharge Survey: 2005 annual summary with detailed diagnosis and procedure data. *Vital Health Stat* 13 2007; (165):1-209.
5. Goldacre MJ, Roberts SE. Hospital admission for acute pancreatitis in an English population, 1963-98: database study of incidence and mortality. *BMJ* 2004; 328:1466-9.
6. Yadav D, Lowenfels AB. Trends in the epidemiology of the first attack of acute pancreatitis: a systematic review [published erratum appears in *Pancreas* 2007;34:174]. *Pancreas* 2006; 33:323-30.
7. Fagenholz PJ, Fernández-del Castillo C, Harris NS, et al. Direct medical costs of acute pancreatitis hospitalizations in the United States. *Pancreas* 2007; 35:302-7.
8. Trapnell JE, Duncan EH. Patterns of incidence in acute pancreatitis. *Br Med J* 1975; 2:179-83.
9. Daniel SP, Marshall MK. Evaluation of the liver: laboratory tests. *Schiff's diseases of the liver*, 8th edn. USA; JB Lippincott publications 1999; 205-239.
10. Abu-Eshy SA. Pattern of acute pancreatitis. *Saudi Med J* 2001;22:215-218.
11. Shayan H, Kopac D, Sample CB. The role of intraoperative cholangiogram in the management of patients recovering from acute biliary pancreatitis. *SurgEndosc* 2007;21:1549-52.
12. Hernandez V, Pascual I, Almela P, Anon R, Herreros B, Sanchiz V, et al. Recurrence of acute gallstone pancreatitis and relationship with cholecystectomy or endoscopic sphincterotomy. *Am J Gastroenterol* 2004;99:2417-23.
13. Nealon WH, Bawduniak J, Walser EM. Appropriate timing of cholecystectomy in patients who present with moderate to severe gallstone-associated acute pancreatitis

- with peripancreatic fluid collections. *Ann Surg* 2004;239:741-49.
14. Alper E, Akay S, Buyraç Z, Aslan F, Alper I, Ünsal B. Endosonography and magnetic resonance cholangiopancreatography show similar efficacy in selecting patients for ERCP in mild-moderate acute biliary pancreatitis. *Turk J Gastroenterol* 2012; 23:580-84.
 15. Hazem ZM. Acute biliary pancreatitis: diagnosis and treatment. *Saudi J Gastroenterol* 2009;15:147-55.
 16. Petrov MS. Early use of ERCP in acute biliary pancreatitis with (out) jaundice: an unjaundiced view. *JOP* 2009;10:1-7.
 17. Collins C, Maguire D, Ireland A, Fitzgerald E, O'Sullivan GC. A prospective study of common bile duct calculi in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy: natural history of choledocholithiasis revisited. *Ann Surg* 2004;239: 28-33.
 18. Bertolín-Bernades R, Sabater-Ortí L, Calvete-Chornet J, Camps-Vilata B, Cassinello-Fernández N, Oviedo-Bravo M, et al. Mild acute biliary pancreatitis vscholelithiasis: are there differences in the rate of choledocholithiasis? *J Gastrointest Surg* 2007;11:875-79.
 19. Ito K, Ito H, Tavakkolizadeh A, Whang EE. Is ductal evaluation always necessary before or during surgery for biliary pancreatitis? *Am J Surg* 2008;195:463-66.
 20. Masci E, Toti G, Mariani A, Curioni S, Lomazzi A, Dinelli M, et al. Complications of diagnostic and therapeutic ERCP: a prospective multicenter study. *Am J Gastroenterol* 2001;96:417-23.
 21. Oría A, Cimmino D, Ocampo C, Silva W, Kohan G, Zandalazini H, et al. Early endoscopic intervention versus early conservative management in patients with acute gallstone pancreatitis and biliopancreatic obstruction: a randomized clinical trial. *Ann Surg* 2007;245:10-17.
 22. Al-Qahtani HH, Alam MK, Al-Akeely MH, Al-Salamah SM. Cholecystectomy without intraoperative cholangiogram in gallstone pancreatitis. *Saudi Med J* 2011;32:714-17.